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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF OSTEOPOROSIS AND ASSOCIATED RISK
FACTORS IN WOMEN*****Dr. Muhammad Farhan Abbas, *Dr. Fariha Abbas, **Dr. Muhammad Sohail Asghar*****Rural Health Center Muradabad, Muzaffargarh******Tehsil Head Quarters Hospital, Kot Addu****Abstract:**

Osteoporosis is growing health concern around the globe. This is considered a silent disease and it is growing on fast track in women. The purpose of the study is to determine the prevalence of osteoporosis and its risk factors in women of Multan South Punjab Pakistan

Method:

This cross sectional study is conducted in Multan and total 360 women were analyzed from the time period of October 2017 to October 2018. All the women were non pregnant and their age group was above 15 years to senior citizen. Data was collected by using questionnaire, X-rays and by the bone mineral density test to analyze the osteoporosis.

Results:

Osteoporosis prevalence in this study was found 42.2 percent overall and its prevalence in women having age group of 45 or less was 14.3 % and it was 50.7% in the women whose age group was above 45 years. The significant risk factors for osteoporosis included age, bone fracture, gravidity, life style, and nutrition and lactation period.

Conclusion:

The prevalence of osteoporosis in women is high and the results showed that the factors which are linked with this process are reproductive factors, age life style and any disease history. Better nutrition and awareness about bone health can help to reduce the problem.

Keywords: *osteoporosis, gravidity, lactation, risk factor, bone mineral density*

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INTRODUCTION:

Osteoporosis is considered skeleton disease which weakens bones strength. The disease affects the quality of life of aging population for both sexes. In Pakistan majority of women are suffering from osteoporosis due to their life style and poor quality of food. The consumption of fast food and carbonated drinks has lowered the calcium level of bones. Low level BMD causes the osteoporosis. The low bone marrow density can be detected from the reports of ultrasound, vitamin D 3 tests and from x-ray reports. The burden of disease can be lessened and also can be prevented by adopting healthy lifestyle, calcium intake and good nutrition. In addition the screening test can help in the diagnosis of disease and treatment can help to reduce the problem. According to the report of WHO the calcium intake of Pakistani women are less than 50 % of the normal calcium intake which is recommended by the consultants.

According to Stetzer, 2011 the osteoporosis is affecting and also threatening the health of majority of women in the world. It is a serious health problem. This disease is considered silent. Bone fractures are common in osteoporosis. Bone mass in women is less than as compared to men therefore they are considered at higher risk of the osteoporosis. According to Stovall 2013 it can be said that after every few second the bone fracture occur in women around the world. Low Bone Mineral Density (BMD) almost doubled in last few decades. According to the study conducted by Larijani *et al.*, 2007; Maalouf *et al.*, 2007 the common risk factors for the disease are aging, genetics, smoking, sedentary life style, calcium balance disorder, lack of physical activities and exercise and also bad eating habits.

The appropriate way to prevent the osteoporosis is to modify the life style, improve eating nutritional food; regular intake of calcium and Vitamin D and by involving in physical activity and adopting regular exercise in routine life. Punjab weather is very hot in summer and cold in winter for only few months. Long summer restricts the women in homes and also they are not in habit of working in sun or taking sun exposure for their better bone health.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The cross sectional study was conducted at Nishter Hospital Multan from October 2017 to October

2018. The female who were willing to participate in the study were registered and total of 360 women participated in the study. The female above 15 years were included in the study and pregnant women were excluded from the study. For better analysis the age group was defined in two main groups. One group of women was less than 45 years of age and before menopause. The other group is above 45 years of age and may have menopause. The questionnaire also have two main parts .One part was about demographic characteristics(age, education, location, income, occupation, height, weight, BMI, marital status, parity, gravidity, lactation time ,menopause, hysterectomy before the age of 45, fracture history if any, diabetes, renal disease, family history of osteoporosis, liver disease, thyroid abnormality, rheumatoid arthritis and any history of hormone replacement therapy).Part two questionnaire is about the lifestyle and about eating habits. The BMD of the patients were measured by the X-rays. Calcium and D 3 tests of the patients were also recommended.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Three hundred and sixty women participated in the study .The age group of the sample was from 15 years to 55 plus (mean \pm SD, 53.35 \pm 12.27) .The women age range from 15 to 25 years were 8.3%, the age group of 26 to 35 were 13.8%.The sample age ranged from 36 to 45 were 20.2%.The participant above 45 years of age were almost 56%.Osteoporosis was not common among young age. Its prevalence from the age group of 15 to 45 years was only14% and the participant older than 45 and above prevalence rate is almost 51%.The majority of the participants was educated and the illiterate and literate participants were only 26% of the total sample. The marital status of the participants were mostly married 75% and unmarried were 25 %. The occupation of the participants varied from student to retired women. House maker was 36% of the participants. The working women were 33.3% and retired personal were counted only11%.The menopausal history of the women were as premenopausal women counted 25 % of the participants and postmenopausal participants counted 75%of the sample. The socio economic condition of the participants was good. Majority of the participants were from middle level income group (64%) and the low income group counted 30.5%.

Table 1 Demographic Characteristics

Age	Case	Percentage
15-25	30	8.33%
26-35	50	13.8%
36-45	80	20.2%
46-55	140	38.8%
Above 55	60	16.6%
Total	360	
Education		
illiterate	60	16.6%
Primary	40	11.1%
Secondary	45	12.5%
Intermediate	55	15.2%
Graduate	110	30.5%
Post Graduate	50	13.8%
Marital status		
Married	270	75%
Unmarried	90	25%
Occupation		
Status	Case	Percentage
Student	70	19.4%
Working	120	33.3%
House Maker	130	36.1%
Retired	40	11.1%
Menopause history		
Premenopausal	90	25%
Postmenopausal	270	75%
Income		
Low level Income	110	30.5%
Middle Level income	230	63.8%
Above Middle level income	20	5%

Osteoporosis is common among women and the risk factor increases in women having the history of bone fractures. The 5 % of the women said that they have the history of bone fracture by themselves and their parents have history of osteoporosis 16.6%. The early menopause and hysterectomy before 44 years of age also increases the risk factor of osteoporosis. Rheumatoid arthritis was observed in 19% of the participants. Sun exposure of the participants was good it was observed 66.6% of the participant spend more than 30 minutes in sun daily. The risk and prevalence of osteoporosis was high in the participants having high no of gravidity and parity. The lactating mothers are also at higher risk of getting osteoporosis.

Medical History

Status	Case	Percentage
Family history of osteoporosis in parent	60	16.6%
History of fracture in parent	15	4%
Fracture history in yourself	20	5%
Menopause age before 44 years	20	5%
Hysterectomy before 44 years	25	6.9%
Hypertension	140	38.8%
Rheumatoid arthritis	70	19.4%
Diabetes	120	33.3%
Sun exposure Less than 30 minutes a day	120	33.3%
Sun exposure More than 30minutes a day	240	66.6%

The osteoporosis studies conducted in different part of the world showed that it is higher in women. Like in India low level of BMD is present among women which is almost 53% described by Aggarwal *et al* 2011. In Iran due to increasing age group of population and transition in demographic the osteoporosis risk has increased considerably and has become a public issue as said by Meybodi *et al*, 2008. Vitamin D is considered vital factor to prevent the silent disease among women and the deficiency of Vitamin D is high in Pakistani women.

Source: <http://ayoti.in/blog/osteoporosis-everything-a-women-should-know/>

The variable which were analyzed in the investigation study the risk factors which were identified for osteoporosis were age, gravidity, history of bone fraction, lifestyle and nutrition habits. High BMI is considered protector for the osteoporosis disease. The increase in age of every 10 years enhances the risk of osteoporosis by 2.17 folds and every unit increased in the BMI helps to reduce the risk of osteoporosis by 5 percent. The osteoporosis cannot be cured but it can be delayed with preventive measurements and by taking supplements. Pakistani women need to improve their life style and improve their nutritional habits. Physical activity with regular exercise can help to reduce the risk of the disease. Vitamin D and calcium sufficient food and supplements can help to reduce the risk. Vitamin D helps in the absorption of calcium which is vital element for healthy bones. The deficiency of vitamin D is present widely in the population of Pakistan. Therefore the Vitamin D supplements are suggested for all age groups so that they can develop strong bones. Sedentary life style in older age has increased the risk of osteoporosis. The absence of exercise and physical activity has resulted in immobility disorder, low bone mass and muscles pain. In present study the participants' response to

regular exercise was very poor. Exercise helps to strengthen muscles and bones which is not present in our culture. Training by the parents and elder for healthy life style is missing from our culture. The women who are involved in physical activity, exercises and also care about their vitamin and calcium intake osteoporosis will not disturb them. Menopause is considered a risk factor in women for osteoporosis as their estrogen level drops in blood which helps to protect bones. Drop in estrogen levels leads to drop in bone density. The estrogen replacement therapy can help to reduce the problem. The women should take bone mineral density test for better idea of their bone health.

CONCLUSION:

The prevalence of osteoporosis is high in women of older age group and the risk factor can be avoided if proper education and training is given to the women from very young age. From colleges to onwards the educational programs should be incorporated so that new generation has strong and healthy bones. The women should adopt healthy life style, regular exercise, calcium and vitamin D rich food and supplement intake can reduce the risk factor. The major risk factor in women were gravidity, lactation

time, sedentary life style, poor eating habits and poor awareness about the bone health.

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